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Launching of the Digital Centre

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ACEEU	Accreditation Council for Entrepreneurial and Engaged Universities
CI	Corporate Identity
DCoE	Digital Centre of Excellence
ECR	Early Career Researcher
EU	European Union
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IP	Internet Protocol
LS	Life Sciences
SER	Socially Engaged Research

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY AND INTRODUCTION

This report aims to introduce and explain the rationale regarding the creation of the Digital Centre of Excellence (DCoE) as a platform for displaying concrete methodological outputs of the BETTER Life project. As such, the DCoE are one of the primary means of communicating and making available the results of the project to the broader public and other academic institutions or quadruple helix actors. It is the intent of the project to use the DCoE to provide information and methodological toolkits relevant to fostering socially engaged research (SER) to early career researchers (ECR) and other potential users of the toolkits provided by the BETTER Life project.

A European DCoE and seven national centres are being set up. The national centres will have a stronger impact in the individual regions and will be set up in national languages. The European DCoE serves as a supra-regional platform. The national centres are similar in structure to the European DCoE but can be specially adapted and expanded to meet regional needs.

The 10 tools developed in the BETTER Life project will be introduced and presented. Furthermore, the various capacity-building activities at institutional and individual level are visualised.

The Digital Centre is hosted by the Accreditation Council for Entrepreneurial and Engaged Universities (ACEEU) – one of the project's beneficiaries. Each partner receives access and can thus edit the content of the respective regional centre.

This report is split into two sections. The first section describes the goals and functions of the DCoE within the project. The second section explains the technical implementation, illustrated with a few screenshots.

1.1 The Digital Centre of Excellence

The DCoE of the BETTER Life project provides an inter-institutional support structure for early career researchers on SER in different project implementation regions. As such, the primary target groups are ECR and other HEIs not currently affiliated with the project. In the context of the project, the DCoE act not only as a platform meant to make visible the outputs of the project, but also as a potential incentive for cooperation with other actors in the field of SER. Thus, the DCoE could directly support the acquisition of new knowledge and foster stronger cooperation among relevant SER stakeholders.

In line with the objectives of BETTER Life:

- the DCoE brings together people from different disciplines from different European countries
- the DCoE supports the development of resources and expertise on the topic of socially engaged research
- the DCoE promotes the diffusion of knowledge in the participating countries.

The focus is on providing tools, learning and information formats and learning experiences from the national centres. Continuous reflection on the formats of the BETTER Life project and thus the DCoE serves to adapt them to the needs of HEI and ECR.

In that context, the DCoE, together with the national centres, will support the ongoing efforts of Work Package 4 "Capacity Building and Community of Practice", including but not limited to:

- the visualisation of the ten toolkits developed to address various challenges related to the advancement of SER in life sciences,
- supporting the implementation of the Virtual Winter School and the on-site Summer School as outlined in the project proposal, as well as
- supporting the bootcamps for ECR and Engagement Managers.

In total, the DCoE consists of eight centres: one EU-wide Digital Centre and seven national centres in the seven project countries. The national centres are working as a showcase and reflection for each region. As such, they can be adapted to the specific regional needs and activities and are especially focused on the activities of the "Think Tanks" - the regional communities of practice and the regional mentorship programmes.

Taking these points into account, the Digital Centre of Excellence must:

- be easily accessible,
- meet EU safety and security standards,
- be easy to manage,
- be compatible with other websites and platforms of the project partners,
- use the English language - as well as the local languages for the national centres, and
- allow an evaluation of their outreach and effectiveness via click and engagement numbers.

DIGITAL CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

2.1 Hosting of the Centre and the Tools

The Digital Centre is hosted by ACEEU, who is responsible for maintaining the Centre after the project's conclusion (<https://www.better-life-digital.eu/>). The server is located in Germany.

At least ten toolkits will be hosted on the Website of the DCoE, which range from simple toolkits such as scientific guidelines to more complex self-evaluation toolkits and include innovative approaches such as educative (board-)games. Some tools require the development of a special platform, and as such, the various project partners develop these tools independently and adapt them to regional needs. Hence, they are hosted on a separate platform and made available on the DCoE through links and embedding. A common layout is guaranteed via the Corporate Identity (CI) of the BETTER Life project.

2.2 Editing the Content

BETTER Life uses WordPress blogs and the website building plugin Elementor (<https://elementor.com/>, provided by ACEEU). This way, each partner will be able to add, adapt and modify content to its regional Digital Centre. To this end, accounts and access structures are set up, and, if necessary, internal training courses are held.

The layout of the website corresponds to the design developed in the project.

Partners have the autonomy to add, adapt, and modify content according to regional needs and preferences in the National Centres. Whether updating resource materials, sharing project updates, or highlighting local initiatives, partners have the tools and flexibility to curate content that resonates with their target audience.

Recognizing the importance of equipping partners with the necessary skills and knowledge, internal training courses are offered to familiarize users with the WordPress

and Elementor platforms. These training sessions provide hands-on guidance on content editing, layout customization, and basic website maintenance, empowering partners to navigate the digital landscape with confidence and proficiency.

While partners have the flexibility to customize content, the layout and design of the website adhere to the overarching design framework developed within the project. This consistency ensures brand cohesion across regional Digital Centres, reinforcing the project's identity and enhancing user recognition and trust. By maintaining a unified visual identity, the Digital Centre presents a cohesive and professional image to stakeholders and visitors alike.

2.3 Safety and Security

The website uses SSL encryption. The private policy is hosted at <http://www.better-life-digital.eu/privacypolicy>. ACEEU is responsible for it. The disclaimer is hosted at <http://www.better-life-digital.eu/disclaimer>.

The website uses Google Analytics and thus cookies. They are used in accordance with German data protection regulations (GDPR). Content to the use of cookies is provided when visiting the website for the first time.

The website collects content needed for Google Analytics, especially IP, browser, system information and referral. In the future there might be a newsletter system. In this case the website would collect email address, first name and last name.

The BETTER Life Digital Centre itself does not manage participants. Single tools might but these will be hosted on their own servers and thus the management is on the respective websites.

2.4 Evaluation of the use of the Digital Centre

The success of the Digital Centre hinges not only on its creation but also on its ongoing relevance and usefulness to our users. To ensure its effectiveness, we will employ comprehensive analytics tools provided by Google to track various metrics such as visitors, unique visits, page visits, and more. These analytics will serve as vital indicators of the Digital Centre's performance and user engagement.

Tracking User Engagement

By closely monitoring visitor metrics, we can gain valuable insights into how users interact with the Digital Centre. Metrics such as time spent on the platform, popular pages visited, and user demographics will provide a detailed picture of user behaviour. Additionally, tracking the frequency and duration of return visits will indicate the level of satisfaction and ongoing interest among users.

Utilizing Download Metrics

In addition to tracking website visits, we will monitor the number of downloads for various resources available through the Digital Centre. This metric will be particularly insightful in assessing the usefulness and relevance of downloadable materials such as guidelines and templates. By analysing download trends over time, we can identify popular resources and tailor future content development efforts accordingly.

User Feedback and Iterative Development

In addition to quantitative metrics, we will actively solicit feedback from users to gauge their satisfaction and gather insights for improvement. User feedback will inform iterative development cycles, allowing us to address pain points, incorporate new features, and refine existing content. By fostering an ongoing dialogue with our user community, we can ensure that the Digital Centre remains a valuable and indispensable resource.

Armed with comprehensive analytics data, we will adopt a proactive approach to continuously improve the Digital Centre. Regular reviews of usage metrics will enable us to identify trends and patterns, allowing us to make informed decisions about content development and platform enhancements. Tools and resources that demonstrate high levels of user engagement and download activity will receive priority attention for further development and updates. The evaluation of the Digital Centre's use will be a dynamic and ongoing process, guided by comprehensive analytics, user feedback, and a commitment to continuous improvement. By leveraging data-driven insights, we can optimize the platform to meet the evolving needs of our users and maximize its impact on project success.

2.5 Navigation Structure of the EU Centre Website

The structure of the EU Centre Website follows the main objectives of the DCoE. Next to the landing page, the following tabs are created:

- About us
- Toolkit
- HEI Self-assessment
- Capacity Building
- Community
- National Centres
- Contact us

The **landing page** provides information about the goals and contents of the DCoE. It also contains links with brief descriptions of the other tabs. It includes reference statements from team members and a section of Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ).

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Fig 1. Landing page (date: 14. 11. 2023)

Fig 2. Landing page (date: 14. 11. 2023)

The tab **"About us"** contains information about the goals of the BETTER Life project, its vision and mission. The possibility of posting a short video is provided.

Fig 3. "About us" (date: 14. 11. 2023)

The **"HEI Self-assessment"** tab will present the self-assessment of work package 5 when the tool is completed. Access to the tool will be provided.

The **"Toolkit"** tab briefly introduces all ten tools, and link to an extra tab or another web page for each tool. The 10 tools are presented in an overview with graphics in a standardised basic design and are then presented in their specifics on the next page.

Fig 4. Overview about the tools (date: 28. 03. 2024)

Fig 5. Example for the description of a tool (date: 14. 11. 2023)

The following tools are presented with a brief description on the main tool page.

Taking different perspectives

BETTER Life’s serious, educative boardgame allows participants to better understand the need for and advantages of collaboration amongst Quadruple Helix actors. The game focuses on teaching the importance of engaging science and cooperative initiatives to address and manage societal and environmental challenges. The tool is played live, the description and instructions are stored in the DCoE.

BL-SER Self-Reflection Tool

BL-Social Engaged Research (SER) is a self-reflection tool tailored for early career researchers (ECRs) keen on exploring, comprehending, and enhancing their engagement with societal actors, particularly with non-academic audiences. This tool serves as a clear framework, guiding ECRs through identification, prioritization, and action planning in

specific key areas of engagement, based on the BetterLife standards. A link to the tool is provided.

Fig 6. Access to the Self-reflection tool (date: 28. 03. 2024)

Academic Bridge

It serves as an invitation to local authorities to participate in our digital platform (Academic Bridge), a comprehensive tool to foster collaboration between local authorities and the academic community. The access to the tool is provided.

[Czech version \(česká verze\)](#)

[Manual for Students and Early-Career Researchers on How to Contact Municipalities Based on the Academic Bridge Matchmaking Map](#)

[Instructions on how a researcher can find the email addresses of municipalities on their websites, create a survey, and send it to mayors](#)

The Academic Bridge's Matchmaking Map is an innovative tool designed to link municipalities across the European Union with academic institutions and experts. By showcasing municipalities and their specific areas of interest, from environmental sustainability to urban planning and social development, the map serves as a digital meeting ground. Municipalities interested in harnessing academic knowledge and expertise for local development are encouraged to submit their applications, including key collaboration interests and contact details. The platform offers a unique opportunity for municipalities to enhance their visibility, engage in collaborative problem-solving, and build capacity

Fig 7. Access to the Academic Bridge tool (date: 28. 03. 2024)

Promote your Research Communication

Toolkit Promote your Research Communication is designed as a user-friendly guidelines to assist researchers in promoting their findings, primarily through social media, to Quadruple Helix actors. It consists of 6 chapters, written as instructions for early career researchers, teaching and research staff in life science to build a strong basis for the greater relevance and accountability and transparency of research outcomes. The download link is provided.

Stakeholder-specific interactive web-based tool for data analyses, presentation and interpretation with the help of R shiny app

R shiny application makes it possible to create an interactive web surface which makes it possible to interpret, show, figure and analyse data without specific knowledge of statistical programs. This tool can be appropriate for the presentation of data, however, for scientific papers there is a need for further – more detailed analysis with some

statistical programs. We developed some shiny apps, that can be useful for SER in LS, and that can be extended with more similar apps, if needed. The download link is provided.

Visual Methodologies for Landscape Observatory

Visual Methodologies for Landscape Observatory is a training course for implementing and utilizing visual tools to work and communicate with the community and interested stakeholders on spatial and landscape planning approaches to landscape enhancement and raising the quality of life. It is an approach to unifying the production of art and visual communication methods to scientific and landscape research. The download link is provided.

Design Thinking for the co-design of public open spaces

The Design Thinking toolkit is a practical guide that aims to provide a comprehensive approach to help users in the co-design of public open spaces. It is based on the principles of Design Thinking and offers a range of strategic tools and actionable steps aimed at delivering integrated solutions through measures that include identifying stakeholders and understanding the needs of the local community. The download link is provided.

Integrating Citizens' Perceptions of Urban Environmental Quality into Inclusive City Planning Processes

This guideline places a specific focus on urban nature. The guidelines provide a framework for classifying urban ecosystem disservices. It aims to understand their specific characteristics in diverse urban contexts and suggests mechanisms for mediating citizen preferences and addressing disservices through effective management interventions, communication strategies, and awareness campaigns. Central to the guidelines is a decision-making tree. Download links are provided.

Human ecosystem integration LAB

(Human) Ecosystem Integration Lab will serve as a digital instrument, found within a dedicated tab on the BETTER Life website. This tool is designed for the active participation of Quadruple Helix stakeholders—universities, businesses, administrations, and NGOs—in engaging with the community. Its focus lies in facilitating discussions and collaborations related to research in life sciences. The access to the tool is provided.

Fig 8. Access to the LAB (date: 28. 03. 2024)

Empowering Growth Through Guided Connections

The mentoring plan is a comprehensive framework designed for fostering effective mentor-mentee relationships in scientific contexts, applicable across European countries and beyond. It includes clearly defined goals such as professional growth, skill enhancement, and effective communication. The plan outlines specific responsibilities for both mentors and mentees, emphasizing regular meetings to discuss progress and provide feedback. The tool accommodates diverse objectives, including networking, ethical conduct, and public outreach. The download will be provided.

The tab "**Capacity Building**" provides an overview of the different activities, such as the virtual spring school, the on-site summer school and the bootcamps. The objectives and activities are presented in an overview. A detailed explanation can be found on the websites of the national centres.

Fig 9. "Capacity Building" (date: 28. 03. 2024)

The example of the Spring School shows how the activities are also promoted via the DCoE. The DCoE is also used as a platform for advertising the Summer School as a joint event.

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Virtual International Spring School for Early Career Researchers in Life Sciences

9th of April to 10th of April 2024, 9-12 a.m. each day

With our International Spring School you will be given an overview of the potential and challenges of socially engaged research and you can explore individual approaches in greater depth as well as learn about interesting methods for enhancing socially engaged research in various workshops and sessions.

We look welcoming Master's students, PhD students and post-docs who want to expand their knowledge of socially engaged research.

Day 1: Expert Lectures on the topics:

- Introduction of socially engaged research
- Expectations regarding socially engaged research
- Challenges and limitations when applying the concept
- Methods and toolkits for socially engaged research
- How to create good space for science communication at universities

Day 2: Parallel Sessions such as:

- Reverse Conceptualization
- Bar Camp
- Scientific Atelier
- Ecosystem Disservices
- Taking different perspectives with a Boardgame

Fig 10. Introduction of the virtual Spring School (date: 28. 03. 2024)

The "**Community**" tab will introduce members of the community of practice at the level of the overall project. In addition, the regional think tanks and the mentorship programmes will be briefly described with their function. For more details, there will be a reference to the national centres.

The tab "**National Centres**" refers to the centres in the Czech Republic, Estonia, Latvia, Poland, Italy, Germany and Serbia.

The tab "**Contact us**" provides the contact information of the team and the link to the BETTER Life Webpage.

2.6 Navigation Structure of the National Centres

The navigation structure of the national centres is based on the structure of the EU Centre. Each national centre will use the national language. Next to the landing page, the following tabs are created:

- About
- HEI Self-assessment
- Toolkit
- Capacity Building
- Community
- Activity and outcomes
- Contact us

The **landing page** provides information about the goals and contents of the DCoE. It also contains links with brief descriptions to the other tabs. In the future, it will be possible to include reference statements from participants and to set up an FAQ.

Fig 10. Landing page Italy (date: 28. 03. 2024)

The tab **"About us"** contains information about the goals of the BETTER Life project and the regional centre. The possibility of posting a short video is provided.

The **"HEI Self-assessment"** tab will present the self-assessment of work package 5 when the tool is completed. Access to the tool will be provided.

The **"Toolkits"** tab will briefly introduce all ten tools when completed, and link to an extra tab or another web page for each tool.

The tab **"Capacity Building"** provides information on the different regional activities, such as the virtual spring school, the on-site summer school and the bootcamps, in detail.

Fig 10. Introduction of the virtual Spring School (date: 28. 03. 2024)

The **"Community"** tab will introduce regional members of the think tanks and the community of practice. In addition, the regional mentorship programmes will be presented.

The tab **"Activity and Outcomes"** can be used for further regional activities. In addition, results for the region can be presented here.

The tab **"Contact us"** shows the contact information of the regional team.

2.7 Feature Options

The Digital Centre of Excellence is designed to be a dynamic and adaptable platform, capable of accommodating changes and enhancements throughout the project lifecycle.

As part of its flexibility, we have identified several feature options that can be seamlessly integrated into the DCoE to enrich user experience and functionality:

- **Tabs** offer a structured way to organize content within the DCoE, allowing users to easily navigate between different sections or topics. By implementing tabs, we can categorize resources, tools, and information, making it simpler for users to locate relevant content efficiently.
- Incorporating **videos** into the DCoE expands the range of multimedia content available to users, enhancing engagement and comprehension. Video content can be used to deliver tutorials, demonstrations, interviews, and other informative materials, catering to diverse learning preferences and communication styles.
- Beyond tabs and videos, the DCoE offers the flexibility to incorporate a variety of **other features** to meet project requirements and user needs. This may include interactive tools, discussion forums, downloadable resources, interactive quizzes, and more. The selection of additional features will be guided by project objectives, user feedback, and emerging trends in digital collaboration and knowledge sharing.

While exploring feature options to enhance the DCoE, it is essential to maintain a balance between functionality and simplicity. While additional features can add value and versatility to the platform, we recognize the importance of keeping the user experience streamlined and intuitive. Complex navigational structures and excessive features can overwhelm users and hinder usability. Therefore, we will prioritize simplicity and ease of use, ensuring that the DCoE remains accessible and user-friendly for all stakeholders.

3. CONCLUSIONS

This report describes the objectives and structure of the DCoE. In terms of the scope of the project, seven national centres will be established in the partner countries in addition to an EU Centre.

Both the tools themselves and the capacity building activities, in which the tools are used, are presented in an informative and clear manner. The DCoE supports the visibility of the tools and thus promotes their future use. The DCoE can also be used to improve and further develop the tools as it can also be contacted and thus feedback on uses/applications of the tools be provided by us based on inquiries from people that visited the DCoE.

The national centres are also being developed in parallel with the further development of the DCoE. These will be particularly important in the implementation phase. All products of the BETTER Life project will be critically reviewed and adapted where necessary.